

1 Accurate and simple digital volume correlation using pre- 2 interpolation

3
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9 **Abstract.** Existing incremental digital volume correlation methods can reduce the number of errors introduced by
10 interpolation calculations in the inverse-compositional Gauss-Newton algorithm (IC-GN) iteration. However, the
11 accuracy of these existing methods is insufficient for some conditions as the curve-fitting method has high
12 computational efficiency but lacks accuracy. A simple pre-interpolation method is proposed to improve the accuracy
13 and computational efficiency of digital volume correlation. First, the pretreatment of a deformed volume image is
14 calculated by the cubic spline interpolation method with the most often chosen interpolation step of 1/2 sub-voxel.
15 Next, the pre-interpolation is calculated only once and the block calculation techniques solve the memory problem.
16 Then, the reference sub-volume in the updated reference volume image is translated into the nearest half-integer
17 voxel position instead of the integer voxel position or other sub-voxel positions. The pre-interpolation method is
18 applied to both the IC-GN and the curve-fitting method. Experimental results show that the maximum mean bias
19 error and the maximum standard deviation of the improved IC-GN are reduced by 34% and 75%, respectively. The
20 improved curve-fitting has better accuracy and computational efficiency than IC-GN under small strain and the
21 curve-fitting method can achieve about 3.2 times speedup than IC-GN.

22
23 **Keywords:** digital volume correlation, pre-interpolation, nearest sub-volume offset.

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25 1 Introduction

26 The Digital Volume Correlation Method (DVC) was developed from mature two-dimensional
27 digital image correlation (DIC) technologies by Bay et al.¹ Since 1999, the DVC algorithm has
28 been widely used to quantify the deformation field of materials under external loading.² DVC
29 can contribute to not only a better understanding of the mechanical behavior of materials from
30 the perspective of a microstructural study³ but also to the verification of the results of 3D finite
31 element simulation.⁴ In the past 20 years, many researchers have been committed to improving
32 the accuracy and computational efficiency of DVC algorithms.⁵⁻⁹ The inverse-compositional
33 Gauss-Newton algorithm (IC-GN) algorithm is an advanced matching algorithm¹⁰ that can
34 accurately estimate displacement fields when large deformation occurs. Although the Hessian

35 matrix only needs to be calculated once in this method, its iterative calculation is still time-
36 consuming. Therefore, Pan et al.⁶ used the interpolation coefficient lookup table approach to
37 reduce the amount of calculation, when using the IC-GN algorithm, in order to improve the
38 computational efficiency; they obtained improvement in computational speed but the approach is
39 memory-consuming. The fast Fourier transform algorithm was also introduced into the DVC
40 algorithm for cases of small deformation to improve computational efficiency.⁷ In recent years,
41 with the rapid development of GPU hardware and software, GPUs have been gradually
42 employed to accelerate the DVC algorithm and the computational speed was significantly
43 improved compared to that of a CPU.¹¹ A simple and effective incremental DVC method was
44 proposed by Wang et al.⁸ to reduce redundant interpolation calculations and errors introduced by
45 interpolation calculations in IC-GN iterations. The deformation of different regions in a real
46 material was calculated by Wang et al.⁹ using the self-adaptive DVC approach; the large
47 deformation is calculated using a small sub-volume size while the small deformation is
48 calculated using a large sub-volume size.

49 However, there is still space for improvement in the accuracy and computational efficiency
50 of these algorithms. For example, incremental algorithms performing well in terms of
51 computational speed may have problems with accuracy and system stability. The self-adaptive
52 DVC approach has the disadvantage of programming complexity. The accuracy and stability of
53 the curve-fitting algorithm are relatively poor compared to the IC-GN algorithm; however, its
54 computational efficiency is outstanding.¹² The curve-fitting algorithm would still be a good
55 choice if its accuracy could be improved.

56 In this work, a simple and effective pre-interpolation method is proposed for the DVC
57 algorithm. First, a 1/2 sub-voxel interpolation calculation is performed in advance, using the

58 proposed pre-interpolation method, on a deformed volume image matrix. Then, the sub-voxel
59 displacement is estimated by the DVC incremental algorithm and the curve-fitting algorithm.
60 The pre-interpolation calculation only needs to be carried out once, which reduces the error
61 caused by intensity interpolation of renewed reference correlation points. Finally, the efficiency
62 and capability of the proposed improved DVC approach is demonstrated in practical applications.

63 **2 In-advance interpolation method**

64 *2.1 IC-GN—large strain*

65 Interpolation calculation is a time-consuming task in DVC calculations; it significantly
66 influences the computational speed. As mentioned earlier, Pan et al.⁶ effectively reduced
67 redundant calculations by using the interpolation coefficient lookup table approach to perform
68 sub-voxel interpolation; however, the deformed sub-volume must be recalculated in each
69 iteration. Subsequently, incremental deformation was employed by Wang et al.⁸ to solve the
70 interpolation problem wherein each incremental position of the deformation is mapped to the
71 nearest integer point. Their simulation results show that the calculation efficiency is increased by
72 approximately 2.5 times the initial value and the error caused by intensity interpolation of
73 renewed reference correlation points is reduced. However, according to the results of this
74 algorithm, in cases such as a sub-voxel displacement calculation, the random errors cannot be
75 ignored when the sub-voxel displacement is about 0.5 voxels (assuming a sub-volume size of
76 $41 \times 41 \times 41$ the mean bias error is 0.003). Moreover, the systematic error of the incremental
77 algorithm cannot be ignored when the sub-voxel displacement is about 0.25 voxels or 0.75
78 voxels (assume a sub-volume size is $41 \times 41 \times 41$, stand deviation error is 0.007). The accuracy of
79 the incremental algorithm is far lower than that of the normal IC-GN algorithm in some cases. In

80 this study, the combination of the pre-interpolation method and the incremental algorithm is
 81 proposed in order to solve these problems.

82 A basic 3D IC-GN algorithm flowchart is illustrated in Fig. 1. For each measurement point,
 83 the robust zero-mean normalized sum of squared difference criterion can be optimized through
 84 the sub-voxel displacement determined by the IC-GN algorithm. It can be seen from Eq. (1) that
 85 the deformation submatrix needs to be constantly updated in each iteration; the corresponding
 86 mathematical operation is the interpolation calculation (more details regarding the DVC
 87 algorithm can be found in Ref. 6).

$$88 \quad C_{ZNSSD}(\Delta \mathbf{p}) = \sum_{\xi} \left\{ \frac{f(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p})) - f_m}{\sqrt{\sum_{\xi} [f(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p})) - f_m]^2}} - \frac{g(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}(\xi; \mathbf{p})) - g_m}{\sqrt{\sum_{\xi} [g(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}(\xi; \mathbf{p})) - g_m]^2}} \right\}^2 \quad (1)$$

89 where $f(\mathbf{x})$ and $g(\mathbf{x})$ are the gray intensity values at point $\mathbf{x}=(x,y,z)^T$ in the reference and target
 90 sub-volumes; $\xi=(\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z)^T$ is the local coordinates of integer voxel points in the reference sub-
 91 volume; f_m and g_m represent the mean intensity values of reference and deformed sub-volumes; \mathbf{p}
 92 is the linear deformation vector; $\mathbf{W}(\xi; \mathbf{p})$ is the linear displacement mapping function used to
 93 describe the deformation of the target sub-volume; $\Delta \mathbf{p}$ is the incremental deformation vector;
 94 $\mathbf{W}(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p})$ is the incremental mapping function exerted on the reference sub-volume.

95

96

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the principle of the 3D IC-GN algorithm.

97 Since the general CT volume image matrix exceeds $1000 \times 1000 \times 1000$ voxels and reduces the
 98 memory requirement, the pre-interpolation is usually set to $1/2$ sub-voxel interpolation. In this
 99 work, the interpolation coefficient α is employed to represent the number of interpolation
 100 segments between two points; α is a positive integer. In Figs. 2(a) and (b), the pre-interpolation
 101 calculation when $\alpha = 2$ is briefly explained. For example, as shown in Figs. 2(a) and (b), when
 102 taking a matrix with $2 \times 2 \times 2$ voxel size in the deformed volume image and performing cubic
 103 spline interpolation, 19 interpolation points are added at the $1/2$ grid nodes. Then, the $2 \times 2 \times 2$
 104 voxels matrix is converted into a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ voxels matrix and the number of nodes changes from 8
 105 to 27.

106
 107 **Fig. 2.** Schematic illustration of the implementation of cubic spline interpolation with $\alpha = 2$: (a) local interpolation unit
 108 comprised of $4 \times 4 \times 4$ voxels; (b) interpolation block surrounded by 8 integer voxel points (blue) and 19 half-integer voxel points
 109 (green); and (c) schematic of the nearest sub-volume offset approach for incremental DVC.

110 The interpolated deformation matrix is $2^3-1=7$ times larger than the original matrix when $\alpha =$
 111 2. Although it needs to occupy a massive amount of memory, this problem can be overcome
 112 using block calculation techniques (as shown in Fig. 3). According to the memory of a computer,
 113 the original matrix can be partitioned in different blocks. s is the maximum displacement, M is
 114 the sub-volume size, and the deformed block volume image is bigger than the reference block
 115 volume image.

116 A schematic illustrating the brief flow of the DVC increment algorithm when $\alpha = 2$ is shown
 117 in Fig. 2(c). According to the 1st-order shape function, the incremental displacement vector of the
 118 updated measurement point can be estimated by:⁸

$$\begin{aligned}
 \begin{bmatrix} u(x, y, z) \\ v(x, y, z) \\ w(x, y, z) \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} u(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) \\ v(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) \\ w(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) \end{bmatrix} + \\
 &\begin{bmatrix} u_x(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) & u_y(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) & u_z(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) \\ v_x(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) & v_y(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) & v_z(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) \\ w_x(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) & w_y(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) & w_z(x_{1/2\text{int}}, y_{1/2\text{int}}, z_{1/2\text{int}}) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} (x - x_{1/2\text{int}}) \\ (y - y_{1/2\text{int}}) \\ (z - z_{1/2\text{int}}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

120 where (x, y, z) is the coordinate of the updated reference measurement point; $x_{1/2\text{int}} = \text{round}(x)$,
 121 $y_{1/2\text{int}} = \text{round}(y)$, and $z_{1/2\text{int}} = \text{round}(z)$ are coordinates providing the location of the nearest half-
 122 integer voxel of coordinate point (x, y, z) ; the vector can be defined as the center point of the
 123 offset reference sub-volume. u , v , and w are three displacement components and $u_x, u_y, u_z, v_x, v_y,$
 124 $v_z, w_x, w_y,$ and w_z are nine displacement gradient components.

125 In the conventional IC-GN algorithm, the gradients of the intensity within the reference sub-
 126 volume $\nabla f(f_x, f_y, f_z)$ are gradients under integer voxel conditions. Since the deformed volume
 127 image matrix is interpolated, the differential formula needs to be corrected as:

$$\nabla f = \left(\frac{\partial f(\mathbf{x} + \xi)}{\partial x} \quad \frac{\partial f(\mathbf{y} + \xi)}{\partial y} \quad \frac{\partial f(\mathbf{z} + \xi)}{\partial z} \right) / \alpha \quad (3)$$

129 where α is the interpolation coefficient.

130

131

Fig. 3. Schematic of the block calculation method (s is the maximum displacement and M is sub-volume size).

132

2.2 Curve-fitting—small strain

133

In real DVC strain analysis, the strain error is difficult to control if the deformation is too large.

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Generally, the average strain level of the material is small (usually less than 5%); however, the

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local strain may be large (for example, the shear strain of some shear bands may exceed 20%). It

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is time-consuming to fully utilize the IC-GN algorithm in terms of calculating small strains. In

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the iterative process of the IC-GN algorithm, the calculation of the multiplication and inversion

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of the remaining matrices is still very large, even though the Hessian matrix only needs to be

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calculated once. In the DIC algorithm, the computational speed of the curve-fitting algorithm is

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seven times that of the IC-GN algorithm;^{12,13} the computational speed difference between these

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two algorithms will be more disparate in the DVC algorithm. Therefore, the curve-fitting method

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is more suitable for calculating small deformation regions. Three algorithms, including the

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curve-fitting method, gradient-based method, and the Newton method, were compared in terms

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of calculation accuracy and stability.¹² The Newton method has the best calculation accuracy and

145 stability; the gradient-based method is the second; the curve-fitting method is the worst (the
 146 accuracies and stabilities of the Newton method and IC-GN are almost the same¹³). The accuracy
 147 and stability of the curve-fitting method can barely meet the calculation requirements. In addition,
 148 the pre-interpolation calculation method described in Section 2.1 is also applied to the curve-
 149 fitting algorithm in order to improve the accuracy and stability.

150 First, the location of the extreme point of the zero-normalized cross-correlation (ZNCC) is
 151 calculated by the integer search algorithm; the ZNCC function is established at the extreme point.
 152 The ZNCC function can be set as $C(x,y,z)$ and the general curve-fitting equation is a ternary
 153 quadratic function:¹⁴

$$154 \quad C_{ZNCC} = \frac{\sum_{\xi} \{ [f(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p})) - f_m] \cdot [g(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}(\xi; \mathbf{p})) - g_m] \}}{\Delta f \cdot \Delta g} \quad (4)$$

$$155 \quad C(x, y, z) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2y + a_3z + a_4xy + a_5xz + a_6yz + a_7x^2 + a_8y^2 + a_9z^2 \quad (5)$$

156 In some research, the least squares method is used to solve the equation parameters;^{12,15}
 157 however, the least squares method involves complicated and time-consuming matrix operations.
 158 The explicit method is used for acceleration while the accuracy and stability of the existing
 159 explicit calculation method are insufficient.¹⁴ Therefore, this method needs to be improved and
 160 solved using Eq. (12), which can be found in the appendix where detailed derivation processes
 161 are included.

162 **3 Experimental verification using numerical tests**

163 *3.1 Accuracy of the proposed DVC method*

164 In this work, a $100 \times 100 \times 100$ voxel size referencing a 3D speckle pattern ($R=4$ voxels, $s=12,000$)
 165 was first generated, as shown in the inset of Fig. 4(a). Then, according to the Fourier shift

166 theorem,¹⁶ ten pure rigid body translation volume images were generated as the deformed
167 volume images. Along the z direction, the displacements range from 0 to 1 voxel (0.0, 0.1, 0.2,
168 0.3, ..., 0.9, 1.0 voxel); the displacements of the x direction and y direction are zero. The random
169 Gaussian noise with a mean value of zero and a variance of four was added to the previous
170 eleven volume images. All DVC analyses were calculated by DVC software written using
171 MATLAB 2018b language on a desktop computer (i7-6700 CPU 3.40 GHz and 8 GB RAM); the
172 free GUI can be found at the following website: <https://github.com/lichengshengHK/FastDVC>.

173 The result of the IC-GN algorithm represents the existing incremental DVC algorithm result
174 when $\alpha = 1$; this means that the incremental DVC algorithm proposed in reference⁸ is a special
175 case of the proposed method in this work. As shown in Figs. 4(a) and (b), for the existing
176 incremental algorithm, the accuracy of the algorithm will be significantly reduced to be far from
177 the accuracy of the conventional IC-GN algorithm when the sub-voxel displacement is in a
178 certain range. Moreover, 1/2 sub-voxel interpolation is performed on the deformed volume
179 image when $\alpha = 2$; the result of IC-GN calculation shows that the insufficiency of the
180 incremental algorithm can be effectively improved. Particularly, the maximum mean bias error is
181 reduced by 34% and the maximum random errors are reduced by 75% when the sub-voxel
182 displacement is between 0.4 and 0.6 voxels. The improvement of the mean bias error and random
183 error is very significant. According to the trend of the curves, the period and amplitude of the
184 mean bias error curves of $\alpha = 2$ are about half of those of the mean bias error curves of $\alpha = 1$.
185 Since the interpolation calculation is completed before the formal DVC calculation, the
186 interpolation calculation time can be almost ignored; however, the improvement of the accuracy
187 and stability of the algorithm is particularly remarkable. Furthermore, the accuracy of the DVC

188 algorithm is very close to that of the traditional IC-GN algorithm when $\alpha = 2$. The specific
 189 comparison of algorithms can be found in Ref. 6.

190
 191 **Fig. 4.** Measured z displacements as a function of sub-voxel displacement estimated by different α and different sub-volume sizes:
 192 (a) mean bias error and (b) standard deviation error of the proposed DVC method of IC-GN method; (c) mean bias error and (d)
 193 standard deviation error of curve-fitting method.

194 As shown in Figs. 4(c) and (d), the mean bias error of the curve-fitting method is close to that
 195 of the IC-GN method when $\alpha = 1$; the maximum error is about 0.003 voxels. However, the
 196 difference between the random errors of these two algorithms approaches one order of
 197 magnitude. Therefore, it is unreasonable to use the curve-fitting method to estimate the sub-
 198 voxel displacement directly. The curve-fitting calculation is much more accurate compared to the

199 existing IC-GN algorithm when the deformed volume is pre-interpolated by a 1/2 sub-voxel ($\alpha =$
200 2). Not only can the mean bias error of sub-voxel displacement be reduced nearly ten times, but
201 the random errors can also be well controlled, which is very close to the random errors of the IC-
202 GN algorithm and fully meets the requirements of a real calculation. The pre-interpolation
203 method can effectively improve the calculation accuracy and stability of the curve-fitting method
204 while retaining the outstanding advantages of high computational efficiency and simple
205 programming.

206 The interpolation coefficients are set as $\alpha = 1,2,3,4$ and the window sub-matrix is set to the
207 sub-volume size of $41 \times 41 \times 41$ in order to verify the accuracy and stability of the algorithm under
208 different interpolation coefficients α . Calculation results are shown in Fig. 5 and it can be seen
209 that the IC-GN algorithm has better accuracy and stability. The mean bias error and standard
210 deviation (SD) error of the IC-GN algorithm gradually decrease when the interpolation
211 coefficient α increases from 1 to 3. However, the stability of the IC-GN algorithm deteriorates
212 and mutations occur in some sub-voxel displacement when $\alpha = 4$. In addition to memory
213 consumption, the accuracy of the algorithm can be improved by appropriately increasing the
214 interpolation coefficient α .

215 The accuracy and stability of the algorithm are improved when the interpolation coefficient α
216 increases from one to two. However, the curve-fitting algorithm is less fortunate than the IC-GN
217 algorithm when the interpolation coefficient $\alpha > 2$; meanwhile, the mean bias error of the
218 algorithm becomes very unstable. Moreover, the SD error increases by nearly seven times its
219 initial value. In these cases, the curve-fitting algorithm cannot meet the calculation accuracy
220 requirements. It can be illustrated from the above analysis that some interpolation errors could be

221 easily caused if the interpolation coefficient is too large, affecting the accuracy and system
 222 stability of the DVC algorithm.

223
 224 **Fig. 5.** Measured z displacements as a function of sub-voxel displacement estimated by different α : (a) mean bias error and (b)
 225 standard deviation error of the proposed DVC method of the IC-GN method; (c) mean bias error and (d) standard deviation error
 226 of the curve-fitting method.

227 Since the accuracy and stability of the algorithm could not be improved by the increase in the
 228 interpolation coefficient, it is necessary to find the optimal α . The memory requirement is
 229 increased by 27 times its initial value when the interpolation coefficient $\alpha = 3$. The memory
 230 requirement is sharply increased to 64 times its initial value when the interpolation coefficient α
 231 = 4, seriously reducing the applicability of the algorithm. Considering the calculation accuracy

232 and memory consumption of the algorithm, the interpolation coefficient $\alpha = 2$ is the best choice.
 233 This not only ensures calculation accuracy but also does not occupy a massive amount of
 234 memory.

235 Moreover, as shown in Fig. 6, the curve-fitting algorithm has better accuracy than the IC-GN
 236 algorithm when $\alpha = 2$. The SD of those two algorithms are similar; however, the mean bias error
 237 differs. The mean bias error of curve-fitting is 15 times less than that of IC-GN. Although curve-
 238 fitting can only deal with small strain deformation of materials, the improved curve-fitting not
 239 only has good accuracy but also has very high calculation efficiency. Therefore, it has a very
 240 high utilization value in small strain situations.

241
 242 **Fig. 6** Comparison of accuracy between the curve-fitting algorithm and IC-GN algorithm with $\alpha = 2$, sub-volume size is
 243 $41 \times 41 \times 41$: (a) mean bias error and (b) standard deviation error.

244 3.2. Computational efficiency of the proposed DVC method

245 The proposed algorithm has better accuracy and stability when the interpolation coefficient $\alpha = 2$.
 246 In this section, the computational efficiencies of the two algorithms under different conditions
 247 are compared. Selecting $\alpha = 1$ and 2, the computational speeds of the curve-fitting method and
 248 the IC-GN method are compared. The IC-GN algorithm has the same computational speed as

249 existing incremental DVC algorithms when $\alpha = 1$. Due to the use of different programming
 250 languages and computer configurations, the computational speed in this paper is slower than that
 251 in Ref. 8 (MATLAB programs are much slower than C++ in general). As shown in Fig. 7, the
 252 computational speed of the curve-fitting method can reach 757.38 points/s and the improved IC-
 253 GN algorithm can reach 237.35 points/s when $\alpha = 2$ and sub-volume size is $41 \times 41 \times 41$. The
 254 computational speed of the curve-fitting algorithm is 3.2 times that of the IC-GN algorithm. It
 255 can be seen that the curve-fitting algorithm is much faster than the IC-GN algorithm. The
 256 computational speed of the small deformation region in the material can be greatly improved and
 257 the displacement of the large deformation region can also be accurately estimated when
 258 calculating the strain field of a real material.

259
 260 **Fig. 7.** Comparison of experimental computational speed of the improved IC-G methods to the improved curve-
 261 fitting method using various sub-volumes (the computation speed of the IC-GN algorithm with $\alpha = 1$ is considered
 262 the standard)

263 4 Discussion and Conclusions

264 In this work, a pre-interpolation method is proposed that typically uses a $1/2$ sub-voxel
 265 interpolation. It was only necessary to calculate the pre-interpolation once and the reference sub-

266 volumes in the updated reference volume image automatically translated into the nearest half-
267 integer voxel position. Therefore, the redundant sub-voxel interpolation calculation was avoided
268 completely. Compared with the integer increment algorithm, the proposed method can improve
269 the accuracy and retain high computational efficiency. Additionally, the curve-fitting algorithm
270 was improved by the pre-interpolation method, whose accuracy and computational efficiency
271 improved significantly. It was also found that if the interpolation coefficient larger than two, the
272 error of the IC-GN algorithm and the curve-fitting algorithm increases; simultaneously, the
273 memory requirement also increases significantly.

274 The simulation results show that the proposed improved DVC algorithm has better
275 performance in accuracy, computational efficiency, and ease of implementation compared to the
276 already existing DVC algorithm. In the MATLAB programming environment, the computational
277 speed is increased by 1-3.2 times the original value, which can effectively improve the accuracy
278 and efficiency of the DVC algorithm. Future studies will investigate how to use IC-GN and
279 curve-fitting algorithms more effectively.

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288 **Appendix**

289 This is the curve-fitting method

290 In this appendix, the steps of solving the curve-fitting Eq. (5) are illustrated in detail. First, for

291 the convenience of writing, the 19 nodes in the cube lattice are marked as follows:

$$\begin{cases}
 C_1 = C(0,0,0) & C_{11} = C(-1,1,0) \\
 C_2 = C(1,0,0) & C_{12} = C(1,0,1) \\
 C_3 = C(-1,0,0) & C_{13} = C(-1,0,-1) \\
 C_4 = C(0,1,0) & C_{14} = C(1,0,-1) \\
 C_5 = C(0,-1,0) & C_{15} = C(-1,0,1) \\
 C_6 = C(0,0,1) & C_{16} = C(0,1,1) \\
 C_7 = C(0,0,-1) & C_{17} = C(0,-1,-1) \\
 C_8 = C(1,1,0) & C_{18} = C(0,1,-1) \\
 C_9 = C(-1,-1,0) & C_{19} = C(0,-1,1) \\
 C_{10} = C(1,-1,0)
 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

293 instrumental variables:

$$\begin{cases}
 h_0 = C_1 \\
 h_1 = (C_2 - C_3) / 2 \\
 h_3 = (C_4 - C_5) / 2 \\
 h_4 = (C_6 - C_7) / 2 \\
 h_5 = (C_8 + C_9 - C_{10} - C_{11}) / 4 \\
 h_6 = (C_{16} + C_{17} - C_{18} - C_{19}) / 4 \\
 h_7 = (C_2 + C_3) / 2 - C_1 \\
 h_8 = (C_4 + C_5) / 2 - C_1 \\
 h_9 = (C_6 + C_7) / 2 - C_1
 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{cases}
 p_1 = (C_8 + C_{10} - C_{11} - C_9 + C_{12} + C_{14} - C_{15} - C_{13}) / 8 \\
 p_2 = (C_8 + C_{11} - C_9 - C_{10} + C_{18} + C_{16} - C_{19} - C_{17}) / 8 \\
 p_3 = (C_{15} + C_{12} - C_{13} - C_{14} + C_{16} + C_{19} - C_{18} - C_{17}) / 8
 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{cases}
 q_1 = (C_8 + C_{11} + C_9 + C_{10} + C_{15} + C_{12} + C_{13} + C_{14} - C_{18} - C_{16} - C_{19} - C_{17}) / 8 - h_0 / 2 \\
 q_2 = (C_8 + C_{11} + C_9 + C_{10} - C_{15} - C_{12} - C_{13} - C_{14} + C_{18} + C_{16} + C_{19} + C_{17}) / 8 - h_0 / 2 \\
 q_3 = (-C_8 - C_{11} - C_9 - C_{10} + C_{15} + C_{12} + C_{13} + C_{14} + C_{18} + C_{16} + C_{19} + C_{17}) / 8 - h_0 / 2
 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

297 According to the Eq. (6)~(9), the curve-fitting equation parameters can be obtained:

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$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} a_1 = (h_1 + p_1) / 2 \\ a_2 = (h_2 + p_2) / 2 \\ a_3 = (h_3 + p_3) / 2 \\ a_4 = h_4 \\ a_5 = h_5 \\ a_6 = h_6 \\ a_7 = (h_7 + q_1) / 2 \\ a_8 = (h_8 + q_1) / 2 \\ a_9 = (h_9 + q_1) / 2 \end{array} \right. \quad (10)$$

299 the extreme points of the fitting function $C(x,y,z)$ should satisfy the following equations:

300

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial C(x,y,z)}{\partial x} = a_1 + a_4 y + a_5 z + 2a_7 x = 0 \\ \frac{\partial C(x,y,z)}{\partial y} = a_2 + a_4 x + a_6 z + 2a_8 y = 0 \\ \frac{\partial C(x,y,z)}{\partial z} = a_3 + a_5 x + a_6 y + 2a_9 z = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (11)$$

301 solving the Eq. (11) and the sub-voxel displacement is given as:

302

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x = -\frac{a_1 \cdot F_1 + a_4 \cdot F_2 + a_5 \cdot F_3}{2a_7 \cdot F_1} \\ y = \frac{F_2}{F_1} \\ z = \frac{F_3}{F_1} \end{array} \right. \quad (12)$$

303 where

$$304 \left\{ \begin{array}{l} F_1 = b_0 b_5 - b_2 b_3 \\ F_2 = b_1 b_5 - b_2 b_4 \\ F_3 = b_1 b_3 - b_0 b_4 \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} b_0 = a_4^2 - 4a_7 a_8, \quad b_3 = a_4 a_5 - 2a_6 a_7 \\ b_1 = 2a_2 a_7 - a_1 a_4, \quad b_4 = 2a_3 a_7 - a_1 a_5 \\ b_2 = 2a_6 a_7 - a_4 a_5, \quad b_5 = 4a_7 a_9 - a_5^2 \end{array} \right. .$$

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356 **Caption List**

357

358 **Fig. 1** Schematic illustration of the principle of the 3D IC-GN algorithm.

359 **Fig. 2** Schematic illustration of the implementation of cubic spline interpolation with $\alpha = 2$: (a)

360 local interpolation unit comprised of $4 \times 4 \times 4$ voxels; (b) interpolation block surrounded by 8

361 integer voxel points (blue) and 19 half-integer voxel points (green); and (c) schematic of the

362 nearest sub-volume offset approach for incremental DVC.

363 **Fig. 3** Schematic of the block calculation method (s is the maximum displacement and M is sub-

364 volume size).

365 **Fig. 4** Measured z displacements as a function of sub-voxel displacement estimated by different

366 α and different sub-volume size: (a) mean bias error and (b) standard deviation error of the

367 proposed DVC method of IC-GN method; (c) mean bias error and (d) standard deviation error of

368 curve-fitting method.

369 **Fig. 5** Measured z displacements as a function of sub-voxel displacement estimated by different

370 α : (a) mean bias error and (b) standard deviation error of the proposed DVC method of the IC-

371 GN method; (c) mean bias error and (d) standard deviation error of the curve-fitting method.

372 **Fig. 6** Comparison of accuracy between the curve-fitting algorithm and IC-GN algorithm with α

373 $= 2$, sub-volume size is $41 \times 41 \times 41$: (a) mean bias error and (b) standard deviation error.

374 **Fig. 7** Comparison of experimental computational speed of the improved IC-G methods to the

375 improved curve-fitting method using various sub-volumes (the computation speed of the IC-GN

376 algorithm with $\alpha = 1$ is considered the standard)

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